

Seeing Blooms in a New Light: Digital Holography for HAB Monitoring in Lake Erie

Cyanobacteria-driven harmful algal blooms (cHABs) form a significant fraction of all HABs in freshwater systems globally. Among the Laurentian Great Lakes of North America, Lake Erie experiences severe cHAB events, comprising multiple toxic strains of different genera and species, including but not limited to, *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Planktothrix aghardii*, and *Dolichospermum* sp.

The need for water-quality monitoring to safeguard human and aquatic ecosystem health has driven funding for comprehensive monitoring programs, through a combination of ship-based routine sampling, e.g., programs led by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's Great Lakes Environment Research Laboratory (NOAA GLERL), and the development of monitoring nodes at fixed locations across the lake. In parallel, there is also a constant endeavor to develop improved and state-of-the-art tools that can be

integrated into future routine monitoring needs.

Rapid strides in imaging technologies have made them an attractive prospect for in situ (or ship-board) plankton observations, including HAB-focused research, as evidenced by the popularity of the commercially available Imaging Flow Cytobot over the past decade [1–2]. Another promising imaging technique, digital holography, holds tremendous potential for HAB monitoring, with recent initial efforts proving promising [3]. Here, we report on field deployments and testing of an *in situ* holographic imaging system (AUTOHOLO) for monitoring cHABs in the western basin of Lake Erie.

Holography is a method that captures interference patterns resulting from the interaction of an undisturbed reference beam and diffracted light scattered by particles within a sample volume illuminated by a coherent light

source, such as a laser beam [4]. The resulting hologram encapsulates information about the size, shape and position of particles or organisms present in the sampling volume, which can be fully recovered during post-processing.

The AUTOHOLO, custom-built at Florida Atlantic University, has been previously used successfully in several applications, including documenting *Karenia brevis* blooms in the Gulf of Mexico [3]. Its versatile design incorporates flexibility in the optical arrangement to tune the system for specific applications. For example, while the standard operation mode uses a lensless configuration, the addition of a microscope objective in the optical path enables adaptive resolution; resolvable size ranges can vary from a few tens of microns to ~ 2 cm, depending on the optics. Additionally, the variable sampling length (1–20 cm) allows for adjustment of the sample volume based on the particle load/turbidity of the water column.

The geographical focus of the study was the western part of Lake Erie, further sub-divided into three areas of interest: the Detroit River (DR) outflow,

Fig. 1. (A). Map of western Lake Erie, with the three sub-regions where sampling was undertaken highlighted – (1) Detroit River outflow, (2) Western basin transect, and (3) nearshore Maumee Bay; (B). the custom-built *in situ* digital holographic microscope (AUTOHOLO) used in the study; and (C). Field deployment work at Lake Erie.

Fig. 2. (A). Morphological variability of *Microcystis aeruginosa* colonies (small to large); and (B). Collage of various planktonic organisms and non-living (sedimentary) particles from Lake Erie during pre- and peak-bloom periods, captured using our holographic imaging (AUTOHOLO) system.

Western Basin (WB), and the Maumee Bay region (Fig. 1a). The AUTOHOLE (Fig. 1b) was deployed in various modes (point sampling, vertical profiling and buoy-based) to quantify particle abundance and plankton community composition over multiple separate field efforts across 2022–2024. Each campaign (Fig. 1c) was carried out in pre-bloom (early summer, June), peak-bloom (August/September) or post-bloom (October) periods, to characterize the seasonal differences. The deployments focused primarily on two objectives: (a) the deployment and testing of the AUTOHOLE under different conditions and sampling the Lake Erie plankton communities, with a focus on *Microcystis sp.*; and (b) building a Lake Erie specific particle/plankton database to facilitate development of an automated data processing pipeline.

Particle abundances and community composition varied seasonally. During the early summer pre-bloom phase, *Microcystis sp.* was absent as expected; zooplankton (copepods, daphnia), certain diatom species, and non-living (sedimentary) particles were the most frequently observed groups. In August (peak bloom), cyanobacterial species, particularly *Microcystis aeruginosa*, dominated the Western Basin region, with other groups contributing negligibly. *Planktothrix aghardii* and *Dolichospermum sp.* were also frequently observed. Collages of observed *Microcystis* colonies of varying shapes/sizes, along with commonly observed particles and organisms in the datasets, are shown in Fig. 2a and 2b respectively.

Vertical profiles at different transects through the Western Basin re-

vealed decreasing *Microcystis sp.* concentrations with distance from shore, qualitatively consistent with satellite maps of bloom extent over the same time period. Ongoing processing of the data will enable us to: (i) characterize size distributions of *Microcystis* colonies; (ii) resolve high-resolution vertical and temporal variations in the spatial distributions of *Microcystis* colonies; and (iii) examine seasonal trends in plankton community composition, which are expected to shed further light on cyanobacterial ecology in the region.

This study demonstrates the ability of digital holography to detect and quantify HAB-forming (and other planktonic) species abundance in a range of diverse conditions in aquatic systems. While the simplicity of holography offers a compelling approach for in situ HAB monitoring, as with other in situ imaging approaches, bottlenecks and challenges remain in large-scale adoption, especially in remote operations and real-time monitoring networks. Some examples of limitations include data-intensive imagery restricting data transmission rates, biofouling of viewing windows, and reliable species-level classification of observed organisms. Future developments should focus on the integration of lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures for near real-time data processing [5–7].

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Authors

Ahammad Abdullah & Aditya R Nayak, Department of Ocean and Mechanical Engineering, Florida Atlantic University, 777 Glades Rd, Boca Raton, FL, USA; Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute, Florida Atlantic University, 5600 US 1 North, Fort Pierce, FL, USA

Timothy S Moore, Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute, Florida Atlantic University, 5600 US 1 North, Fort Pierce, FL, USA

Karl R Bosse & Michael J Sayers, Michigan Tech Research Institute, Michigan Technological University, 3600 Green Ct STE 100, Ann Arbor, MI, USA

Email corresponding author: anayak@fau.edu

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